

The TwoPhaseComponentialFlow module

1. General description

The TwoPhaseComponentialFlow module is dedicated to the modelling of 2-dimensional two-phase Darcy-scale subsurface flow. It is designed to transport four gas components: (air, hydrogen, methane and carbon dioxide). These gas components can be solved into the water. The following chemical reactions are implemented within the module:

1. cement degradation reaction: sink of CO_2 and H_2O , source of H_2O , change in porosity
2. organic waste degradation (cellulose and plastic): sink of H_2O , source of CO_2 and CH_4
3. steel waste corrosion: sink of H_2O , source of H_2
4. steel surface corrosion (steel drums): sink of H_2O , source of H_2

Further details pertaining to chemical reactions and the calculation of the reaction rates that depend on water availability can be found in the publication by Vehling et al. (2024), along with its supplementary data file and references cited therein. In Vehling et al. (2024), the module is designated by a different name, namely "OpenGeosys-MP-LT".

The rates of chemical reactions 1 to 3 are evaluated at each integration point of a finite element. Similarly, the source and sink terms are also calculated at each integration point. For reaction 4, which is the corrosion of the steel surface, the two integration points closest to the surface are identified for each finite element at the steel surface. The chemical reactivity at these two points depends on relative humidity and pH, and is used to calculate the corrosion rate, as well as the corresponding H_2 steel surface gas generation rate and the H_2O consumption rate. For each integration point, the H_2 steel surface gas generation rate is multiplied by half the length of each edge of the finite element attached to the steel surface. In summary, this means that the surface gas generation rate of the steel surface is lumped on the two nearest integration points as a volumetric source term.

In this module, the chemical reactions are facilitated by the implementation of unique material ids for the materials contained within the geological repository. A total of 14 material ids have been defined. The user is free to set the flow parameters in the project file but the porosity of the concrete and mortar materials connected with cement degradation must be the same as the initial porosity given in the look-up table for the specific mortar or concrete.

The chemical reaction parameters are hard coded for the purpose of modelling a 2d cross section of a low-level waste repository following a general concept proposed by Nagra (2016). The look-up tables provided in the source code have been kindly provided by Georg Kosakowski (Paul Scherrer Institut, Forschungsstrasse 111, 5232 Villigen, Schweiz) via personal communication. A detailed description of cement chemistry and preparation of the look-up tables can be found in Vehling et al. (2024). The actual look-up table used in the module is based on cement degradation batch calculations using the GEM-Selektor (GEMS) v3.3 code, from which the following parameters are extracted at each interpolation point of the look-up table. The amount of CO_2 added and the amount of SiO_2 reacted are used as coordinates: the molar amount of water consumed/released, pH, porosity, and degradation rate for aggregate dissolution are calculated and tabulated.

Hard-coded material ids:

- 0: functional concrete (gallery floor, container walls) - no siliceous aggregates, cement degradation reaction via look-up table for cement carbonation
- 2: mortar for filling gaps between container (local back fill, abbr.: locback; low viscosity mortar) - cement degradation reaction via look-up table
- 3: mortar for vault or cavern back fill, (abbr.: M1) - cement degradation reaction via look-up table
- 4: infill mortar for container and drum back fill (old abbreviation still used in code: bfn; cement degradation reaction via look-up table):
- 5: infill mortar with steel surface on the left |
- 6: infill mortar with steel surface on the right |
- 7: infill mortar with steel surface on the top -
- 8: infill mortar with steel surface on the bot _
- 9: infill mortar with steel surface on the left-bottom | _
- 10: infill mortar with steel surface on the right-bottom _ |
- 11: infill mortar with steel surface on the top-left |-
- 12: infill mortar with steel surface on the top-right -|
- 13: steel waste combined with infill mortar – steel corrosion and cement degradation reaction via look-up table
- 14: organic waste - organic degradation reaction

Material ids not fixed (no chemical reactions), but given in the test for chemical reactions (test folder "test_chem_react")

- 1: shotcrete or liner, no cement degradation reaction
- 15: EDZ (excavation damage zone)
- 16: host rock

Only within the code, the user can change the amount and density of the organic waste (cellulose and plastic) and steel waste. Also, the degradation rates are hard-coded. The appended MATLAB file contains the calculations of waste densities in relation to the conversion from three dimensions to two dimensions.

2. Application example

An application example can be found in the EURAD report: "Deliverable 2.19: Model abstraction techniques for assessing the chemical evolution at the disposal cell scale and applications for sensitivity and uncertainty" (Samper et al. 2024) on pages 48 to 57. The Appendix of this manuscript provides the application example.

3. Newly added features in 2025

Further new features have been incorporated following the publication of the EURAD report D2.19.

3.1. New hard coded look-up tables

Four different look-up tables are available for the degradation of mortar or concrete materials (see list of material ids).

3.2. Drum hull

The thickness of the not yet corroded drum steel hull is tracked. The drum hull remains impermeable even when fully corroded. However, the process of corrosion reaction is halted.

3.3. pH dependent corrosion rate

The steel corrosion rate depends on the water pH and relative humidity. For a relative humidity of 1 the steel corrosion rate is 0.1 μm per year at a pH value of higher than 12. Applying a linear dependence on pH, the steel corrosion rate is multiplied by a pH-dependent factor f_{pH} when pH is below 12. This is calculated as follows:

$$f_{\text{pH}} = 50 - \left(\frac{50 - 1}{1.5} \right) \cdot (\text{pH} - 10.5) \quad \text{if } 10.5 \leq \text{pH} \leq 12$$
$$f_{\text{pH}} = 50 \quad \text{if } \text{pH} < 10.5$$

3.4 Gas generation rate of steel waste

In the updated version, the gas generation rate resulting from corrosion is calculated with the consideration of the amount of steel waste that has not yet undergone corrosion. The H_2 gas generation rate Q_s [mol a^{-1}] for steel waste is computed with a first-order kinetic approach:

$$\frac{\partial m_s(t)}{\partial t} = -m_s(t) \cdot \lambda_s \cdot f_{\text{pH}} \cdot R_\varphi^m$$
$$Q_s = m_s(t) \cdot k_d^s \cdot f_{\text{pH}} \cdot R_\varphi^m$$

where $m_s(t = 0)$ refers to the initial mass of steel waste [kg] and k_d^s represents the amount of gas generated from one kg of steel waste over one year. λ_s denotes the degradation rate from which the half-life $t_{1/2} = \ln(2) \cdot \lambda_s^{-1}$ for the decay can be calculated. R_φ^m is the reactivity factor for mortar depending on relative humidity φ . Further details on the calculation of λ_s and k_d^s can be found in the appended MATLAB file.

4. Benchmark tests

A total of 13 ci tests are carried out to ensure that phase and component transport are working correctly. The results of these tests are then compared against analytical solutions.

An additional ci test covers all chemical reactions in an artificial setup, including a metal waste compartment and a steel drum filled with organic waste. A short test description can be found in the test folder: "Ogs-src\Tests\Data\H2C3".

5. Appendix

Application example of the EURAD report: "Deliverable 2.19: Model abstraction techniques for assessing the chemical evolution at the disposal cell scale and applications for sensitivity and uncertainty" (Samper et al. 2024). Here pages 48 to 57 of the original manuscript are provided.

Outdated model features are marked in red and new model features are added in blue.

4.1 Short description of the ILW disposal cell in clay

4.1.1 General model description

Figure 4-1a illustrates the overall cross-section of a general ILW repository model adopted by UFZ. The model domain represents a gallery constructed in the clay host-rock. The dimensions of the gallery are following a general concept proposed by Nagra (2016). There are a couple of waste containers stacked in a 3-level structure inside of the repository. Two types of waste containers are considered in the model.

- 1) The container with metal waste, marked with red color in Figure 4-1b. Each container is filled with 6640 kg of carbon steel waste. The steel surface area is $0.064 \text{ m}^2/\text{kg}$ (Wieland et al. 2018) leading to a surface area per volume of $127 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}^3$. In order to convert the surface area from 3D to 2D in the numerical model, a conversion factor of 0.75 is multiplied with the steel surface area and applied on the 2D surface area of the metal waste. **The steel corrosion rate is set to $0.02 \text{ }\mu\text{m per year}$ leading to a H_2 gas production of $0.00375 \text{ mol}/(\text{m}^2\text{a})$ when pH is higher than 10.5 (Huang et al. 2021). If the pH value is below 10.5 the corrosion rate increases to $2 \text{ }\mu\text{m per year}$. This pH dependent corrosion rate is adopted from Wieland et al. (2020), which is also used in Huang et al. (2021). Update 2025: (see section 3.3. in the main manuscript)**
- 2) The other type of container is filled with the organic waste (marked with orange color in Figure 4-1b), which is stored in multiple drums. As already described in D2.15 (Blanc et al. 2024), the waste drums are further organized in a 2x3x2 layout in the container (see Figure 4-2), with the surrounding space filled with mortar. Here in the large-scale model, the difference in comparison to the smaller scale model used in D2.15 is that the inner metal tube placed in the D2.15 model has been removed. For accounting the correct amount of organic waste in the third dimension, we have calculated a smaller drum area of $0.374 \text{ m} \times 0.545 \text{ m}$ and a waste area of $0.299 \text{ m} \times 0.436 \text{ m}$, considering a distance between the container mid-point of 2 m in the third dimension. After the removal of the inner tube, there is no metal waste inside of the drums (see Table 4-1). The reduction in total metal quantity is negligible, considering the large amount of metal waste placed in the other type of containers. But still, the model considers H_2 production from the corrosion of the drum metal hull.

Outside of the gallery wall, an excavation-damage-zone (EDZ) is also reflected in the model domain, which is located between the concrete liner and the clay host rock. The entire gallery will be equipped with a concrete liner (light gray color in Figure 4-1b). Between the waste container and the concrete liner, a special M1 mortar is introduced (blue color in Figure 4-1). It has a relatively higher porosity value, with the intention to give more volume to host the gas produced by the degradation and corrosion reactions. The high porosity of the M1 mortar goes along with a high permeability, allowing the gas to move to the top of the gallery. Similar to the configuration of the organic waste containers, the void space between the containers is again filled with the same mortar material.

Figure 4-1: a) Domain and discretization of the gallery model. Description of the disposal concept and design is reported in D2.16 (Samper et al. 2021) Conceptual model formulation; b) Zoom-in view on the cross section of the gallery model. Brown lines show the metal hull of the drums and waste areas are shown in orange.

Figure 4-2: Schematic sketch of the generic waste package. Organic waste (orange) with local back fill mortar (grey) (ACED_T3.3 Deliverable D2.15, Blanc et al. 2024).

Table 4-1. Content of organic waste drum, degradation parameters, gas generation rates and rates for water consumption for two waste groups from Huang et al (2021).

Symbol	Unit	Group 1 (Cellulose)	Group 2 (Polysterene)	Reference
$m(t=0)$	kg	30.6	65.3	This Study (in comparison to the model of Huang et al 2021 the metal waste is emplaced by organic waste)
Mass per volume waste	kg/m ³	234	500	waste per m ³ in waste area
λ	a ⁻¹	$1.89 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$6.51 \cdot 10^{-5}$	Wieland et al 2018, Wieland et al 2020
k_D	mol kg ⁻¹ a ⁻¹	0.07	0.005	Leupin et al 2016
Rate for CO ₂	mol kg ⁻¹ a ⁻¹	$k_D \cdot 3/6$	$k_D \cdot 3/8$	Huang et al 2021
Rate for CH ₄	mol kg ⁻¹ a ⁻¹	$k_D \cdot 3/6$	$k_D \cdot 5/8$	Huang et al 2021
Rate for water consumption	mol kg ⁻¹ a ⁻¹	$k_D \cdot 1/6$	$k_D \cdot 6/8$	Huang et al 2021

Table 4-2. Hydraulic properties used in the gallery model.

Parameter	Symbol	Unit	Local back fill Mortar	Waste matrix	Host rock (Clay)	EDZ	Mortar1**	Concrete
Intrinsic permeability	k	m ²	1e-19	1e-16	4e-20	5e-18	1e-12	5e-19
Porosity	Φ	-	0.076*	0.2	0.18	0.18	0.3	0.2
Residual saturation	S_L^{rel}	-	0.2	0.2	0.4	0.2	0.3	0.2
van Genuchten characteristic (entry) pressure	p_d	Pa	1e6	1e4	4e6	2e6	5e2	1e6
van Genuchten parameter	m	-	0.36	0.5	0.4	0.4	0.5	0.5

* Local back fill mortar porosity changes with cement carbonation and alkali silica reaction (ASR)

** no mortar degradation

Local back fill mortar - Update 2025: In this model, the local back fill mortar (abbreviated to loeback) is also used to fill the void spaces in drums and containers. In the new model, the infill mortar (bfm) is placed inside the drums and the containers. The local back fill mortar (loeback) is only used to fill the gaps between the containers.

In the model configuration, the initial liquid saturation is given with different values for different materials. More specifically, the back fill mortar is considered to have an initial saturation of 0.996, reflecting the fact that there is enough water available after the hydration process. The organic waste was assumed to have an initial saturation of 0.33, similar as the configuration in D2.16 (Samper et al. 2021). The clay host-rock has an initial water saturation of 1. On the pressure side, the initial gas pressure in the gallery is set to 5 MPa. This reflects the hydro-static pressure at 500 m depth below subsurface, and it is also linearly increasing following the hydrostatic pressure gradient. At the domain boundary, a capillary pressure of 0 Pa is set in the model, suggesting that the clay rock at the far-field is fully saturated.

4.1.2 Two-phase multi-phase multi-component model

In order to investigate the controlling factors of the gas production process, the coupled reactive transport model of component based two-phase flow module in the OpenGeoSys (OGS) framework is adopted here. A detailed description of the reactive transport model can be found in Huang et al. (2021). Here in this report, a brief summary of the model is also provided.

For the two-phase module in OGS, the standard Galerkin finite element (FE) method is employed for spatial discretization with a fully implicit backward Euler scheme for the time integration. The concrete, mortar and waste are implemented as porous and permeable medium with two mobile phases, gas and liquid. The gas components are water vapour, nitrogen, methane, hydrogen and CO₂ and can dissolve into the water dominated liquid phase. As mass transport model the generalized Darcy law is implemented in combination with diffusive transport given by Fick's law:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \sum_{\alpha \in \{G,L\}} (N_{\alpha} S_{\alpha} x_{\alpha}^i) + \nabla \left[\sum_{\alpha \in \{G,L\}} N_{\alpha} (x_{\alpha}^i \mathbf{q}_{\alpha} + \mathbf{J}_{\alpha}^i) \right] = F^i \quad [4-1]$$

Where α denotes the gas phase G or the liquid phase L, x is the molar fraction of component i in phase α , S_{α} is the saturation of phase α , and N_{α} represents the phase molar density. F^i is a source or a sink term for each component. The Darcy law is given as:

$$\mathbf{q}_{\alpha} = - \frac{k k_{\alpha}^{\text{rel}}}{\mu_{\alpha}} (\nabla p_{\alpha} - \rho_{\alpha} \mathbf{g}) \quad [4-2]$$

Here ρ_{α} is the phase density and p_{α} is the phase pressure. The diffusive flux \mathbf{J}_{α}^i is obtained by Fick's law:

$$\mathbf{J}_{\alpha}^i = - D_e \nabla x_{\alpha}^i \quad [4-3]$$

where the effective diffusion coefficient D_e is defined as $D_e = \Phi \cdot S_{\alpha} \cdot D_{\alpha}$ is, Here Φ denotes the material porosity and D_{α} is the diffusion coefficient of i in phase α . For unsaturated conditions the capillary pressure p_c has to be taken into account and is obtained by the van Genuchten model:

$$p_L = p_G - p_c \quad [4-4]$$

$$p_c(S_L^{\text{eff}}) = p_d \left((S_L^{\text{eff}})^{-\frac{1}{m}} - 1 \right)^{\frac{1}{n}} \quad [4-5]$$

Here $m = 1 - 1/n$ and n are the van Genuchten parameters and p_d is the characteristic van Genuchten pressure. The effective saturation S_L^{eff} is given by

$$S_L^{\text{eff}} = \frac{S_L - S_L^{\text{res}}}{1 - S_L^{\text{res}} - S_G^{\text{res}}} \quad [4-6]$$

4.2 Relevant output variables

4.2.1 Gas production

The numerical model simulations reveals distinctive gas production processes in containers filled with metal or organic waste. In the metal-filled containers, where the void space between the metal is cemented, simulated pH values remains around 13 during the entire 500 years simulation time. As the pH is relatively high, there is barely any hydrogen producing corrosion of the metal observed. Because of the high saturation condition in container, Alkaline-Silica-Reactions are happening with the consumption of water. However, due to the low reaction rate of ASR, there is no observable impact on the liquid saturation and pH in the container. Due to the presence of high pH value, the molar gas

production rate inside of the metal containers is one order of magnitude lower than those inside the drum containers. Therefore, there is only negligible contribution of gas production from the metal container. However, as ASR is a very slow process, given long enough time, it may cause the pH in the container to drop below 10.5, which may further lead to a completely different metal corrosion rate. Yet, this process is not seen in the current simulation, which only covers the first 500 years.

In contrast, the process in the drum is completely different. Here, the cellulose degradation (fast degradation organics) becomes the main source of CO₂ production. Despite of the high CO₂ production rate in the first 500 years, most of the CO₂ produced in the drum participates in the carbonation reactions with the mortar there. This caused a continuous reduction of pH of the mortar progressing towards the metal hull. At the same time, methane is being produced by the fast degrading organics at the same rate. As there are no local reactions holding it, the methane gas will gradually leave the waste drum (see Figure 4-3b). The gas generation rates are decreasing with a minimal rate because the degradation rate drops along with less amount of degradable organic waste. In comparison to the metal container, the pH value inside of the drum is dropping due to the cement carbonation reactions, it is approaching 10.5 after about 320 years. This then triggers the fast corrosion of the drum metal lid, leading to an increase in the hydrogen production observed in Figure 4-3b. After 500 years the hydrogen and methane fluxes are equal indicating an equal gas production rate for both gases.

4.2.2 Gas and liquid flux at a drum opening and liquid saturation inside of a drum

At the beginning, the mortar inside of the drum and in the container are close to be fully saturated. Therefore, the relative gas permeability of the mortar is very low. Therefore, the produced gases lead to a strong gas pressure increase that leads first to a strong increase of the liquid flux out of the drum (Figure 4-3b). The gas flux is then increasing with increasing gas saturation, having the peak gas flux after 30 years. The initial decrease of liquid saturation leads to an increase of capillary pressure of 0.2 MPa, which reduces the liquid flow out of the drum significantly (Figure 4-3b and d).

After this initial period, the flow regime is then heading to relative stable mode, which lasts between 200 and 300 years. The reason is that there is enough water available to feed the outflow of liquids and the water consuming organic degradation, which is continuously reducing the initial liquid saturation in the mortar and waste. The liquid flow regime is then disturbed by the water consuming steel corrosion leading to a reversal of the liquid flow into the drum. After 450 years the hydrogen production rate and therefore the water consumption become nearly constant. But this does not lead to a constant liquid flow into the drum, because at the same time the liquid saturation of the waste could not be depleted anymore for feeding the organic degradation. It has reached the residual value of 0.2, where the liquids become immobile and chemical reactivity drops. Later than 500 years, a flow regime will be established where the water flux into the drum has to match the water consumption rate of the chemical reaction rate, which will probably decrease due to a decrease of chemical reactivity.

4.2.3 Gas pressure and gas flux at the gallery scale

As the time goes along, the high-pressure zone gradually extends from the containers to the outer spheres of the gallery, and also into the host rock. Driven by the pressure gradient, the produced gas is moving outwards into the clay host rock, as well as moving upwards due to the density effect (see Figure 4-4, e and f). In comparison to the simulation results in a smaller scale reported in D2.15, a distinctive feature in the larger gallery model is the influence of the M1 mortar. From the lower and middle containers, the produced gases are mostly transported horizontally into the M1 mortar using

the easiest conduit to the high permeable M1 mortar. Here the gases can easily move upwards into the gallery roof, where the M1 Mortar is designed as intermediate gas storage. In Figure 4-4a, it can be observed that gas moves faster in the M1 mortar zone (indicated by red arrows). This is also reflected in the 25 and 50 years' results (Figure 4-4c and d). From the upper containers the gas is directly moving upwards into the M1 mortar. After 160 years the gas pressure has increased in total by 0.6 MPa and is slowly increasing further because of the fixed pressure boundary condition. Here a larger modeling area would lead to higher gas pressures within the gallery, especially when the hydrogen gas production of the drums starts to increase.

Figure 4-3: Time series plots showing the hydrological evolution of the upper left drum in the lower right container. Panel (a) shows the location of mesh nodes corresponding to the time plots. Panel (a) show gas fluxes (methane and hydrogen) and liquid flux out of the upper left drum in the lower right container. Displayed gas flux is the sum of diffusive and advective flux. Negative values indicate fluid flow into the drum. Panel (c) shows liquid saturation, (d) liquid pressure and (e) capillary pressure.

Figure 4-4: Gas pressure (colored legend) and gas flux (arrows) after 1, 10, 25, 50, 100 and 160 years of model simulation.

4.2.4 Capillary pressure and liquid flux at gallery scale

The hydrological material parameters have a high impact on the liquid flow field. The van Genuchten characteristic entry pressure of the local back fill mortar is four orders of magnitude higher than the value for the M1 mortar. This has the effect that the local back fill mortar will hold the pore water due to the high capillary effect. Due to the initial gas pressure increase the liquids of the container area (back-fill mortar) are flowing upward and sideward into the M1 mortar which is shown in Figure 4-5a and b. At the upper M1 mortar they stay fixed because of the gravity and at the sideward M1 mortar they can move downwards. At the low part of the gallery the liquids are pushed downwards to the mesh boundary.

After 25 years (see Figure 4-5c), the liquid flux in the upper container area has significantly decreased and the direction has changed downwards. The reason is that the gas pressure is not high enough to overcome the gravity effect and the capillary pressure. After 50 years the liquids, which were pushed into M1 mortar before, are sucked into the container area due to the increased capillary pressure and the increased gas pressure of the M1 mortar.

After 160 years the liquid saturation at the lower containers have decreased to 0.9 and is higher than at the upper containers (Figure 4-6c). The reason is that the gas pressure gradient at the upper containers slows down the liquid flow downwards.

Figure 4-5: Capillary pressure (colored legend) and liquid flux (arrows) after 1, 10, 25, 50, 100 and 160 years of model simulation.

Figure 4-6: Liquid saturation (colored legend) and liquid flux (arrows) after 1, 75 and 160 years of model simulation.

4.3 Summary

In this study we found that the difference of the drum model, which is introduced and studied in D2.15, in comparison with this drum model here, leads to significant differences in gas generation rates for the first 50 years. The emplacement of the metal waste part with organic waste, i.e. increased amount of fast degrading cellulose, increases the methane and CO₂ production rate, but as the cement carbonation reaction consumes the CO₂ and releases water, the water is then available for further degradation of organics. As the fast corroding metal tube and the metal waste inside of the drum is missing in this study, the overall net water consumption rate is much lower leading to lower but more constant gas net generation rate of the first 500 years. The single container study in D2.15 has a higher gas generation rate with a sharp drop after 50 years when available water has been consumed.

The in this study presented gallery scale simulation is one of the first having a detailed resolution of the drum characteristics. This allows more precisely simulations for better performance assessments of the repository. Here The impact of changes of different material parameters is of interest to find parameters leading to a minimization of the gas pressure peak and to predict re-saturation times of the repository. In this study the simulation time does not cover the increase of hydrogen generation of the metal containers due to pH decrease by the ASR reaction. This will happen under saturated conditions after around 1000 years and could potentially lead to a new gas pressure maximum. This study shows that it is unlikely that CO₂ migrates towards the metal containers if there are no fractures in the mortar. Therefore, it is unlikely that cement carbonation leads to a significant drop in pH in the metal containers and increase in corrosion rates. However, this has to be studied/confirmed in additional simulations including a 1000+ years simulation time. The model setup here could be further improved by increasing the model size and the mesh resolution especially at the drums and at the transition areas of materials with large properties changes. **Additionally, the function for calculating the steel corrosion rate could be replaced by a continuous function in dependence of pH.** Update: a linear dependence of the steel corrosion rate has been implemented in the pH range of 10.5 to 12 (see section 3.3. in the main manuscript).

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